

COGNITIVE-SEMANTIC ASPECTS OF POLYSEMY

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Abstract. There is an ongoing debate about the meaning of lexical words, i.e., words that contribute with content to the meaning of sentences. This debate has coincided with a renewal in the study of polysemy, which has taken place in the psycholinguistics camp mainly. This article describes about cognitive-semantic aspects of polysemy and their role in the field of linguistics.

Key words: polysemy in English, aspects of polysemy, cognitive aspects of polysemy, semantic aspects of polysemy.

There is an ongoing debate about the meaning of lexical words, which, as a first approximation, can be characterized as words that contribute with content to the meaning of sentences. The distinction between functional and lexical words is notoriously difficult to make, but we can take it that, typically, lexical words are used to describe and categorize the world, whereas the role of functional words is more structural and language-internal. It has been observed that lexical words do not always contribute with the same conceptual meaning to propositional constructions. In some cases, this is because the word is overtly context sensitive. For instance, an adjective such as tall will express a different conceptual meaning when the standard of tallness is placed at one point of the scale of height than when it is placed at another point. But in many other cases, words are not overtly context sensitive, and yet they fail to express the same conceptual meaning in all occasions.

The three views about word meaning outlined above, correspond to three similar accounts on polysemy, in particular, on how polysemy is represented and stored. Polysemy is the well-known observation that a word has various different but related meanings. In this, it is contrasted with monosemy, on the one hand, and homonymy, on the other. While a monosemous form has only one meaning, a homonymous form is associated with two or several unrelated meanings (e.g., coach;

‘bus’, ‘sports instructor’), and is standardly viewed as involving different lexemes. There is a growing interest in polysemy, especially in the psycholinguistics camp, which focuses on differences in access, storage and representation of polysemous senses homonymous meanings. However, polysemy is also studied from different perspectives, such as computational linguistics pragmatics, psychology, cognitive linguistics, theoretical semantics, and lexicography. As said above, it is possible to group the different views that have been defended concerning how senses are represented and stored into three main theories:

- A. Literalism: each polysemous term has a literal, denotational, meaning. The rest of senses it has are generated on the basis of linguistic rules, coercion, or pragmatic inferences.
- B. Underspecification (core meaning) account: the meaning of a polysemous term is an underspecified, abstract, and summary representation that encompasses and gives access to its different senses.
- C. Overspecification (rich) account: the meaning of a polysemous term includes all its different senses, which are stored in a single representation. Senses are selections of the total meaning of the word.

I will understand literalism with respect to polysemy in the same way as above: basically, a position that can also be described as an instance of overspecification does not count as literalist. Literalism is partly endorsed by Asher, where, as mentioned, he tries to explain a good number of meaning variations in terms of coercion, as well as by representatives of Relevance Theory such as Falkum, and Copestake and Briscoe’s account of some regular polysemies. Recent psycholinguistics tends to favor underspecification and overspecification approaches. What distinguishes one from the other is the question of whether access to the different senses of a word is direct or goes through an intermediate station called “common core”. The common core of, e.g. the different senses of the verb cut could be “change of state in which an entity which exemplifies some kind of connectedness undergoes a process of controlled disconnection”. Whenever a reader

finds the word cut in a text, she activates that common core representation. It may be that she is not required to home in on a more specific sense, and thus this is the only representation that is accessed, even if more specific interpretations are also activated. However, the reader may need to home in on a specific sense of the word. In this case, she would easily retrieve the specific sense from the constellation of senses the underspecific representation gives access to. In this respect, polysemy resolution differs from homonymy resolution, where (a) readers need to home in on a specific meaning as soon as they encounter the homonym, (b) there is a clear bias towards the dominant meaning, and (c) different meanings compete against each other, so that the meaning that is not selected quickly decays. According to Frisson, Klepousniotou et al., MacGregor et al., and others, in polysemy resolution we do not see a strong bias for the most frequent, or dominant, sense. Indeed, senses prime each other no matter which sense is more frequent, and their common activation survives for at least 750 ms. These observations, together with the further observation that words with multiple senses are recognized faster (in lexical decision tasks) than words with less senses and, especially, than homonyms, suggests that the representation and storage of polysemous senses is very different from the representation and storage of homonym meanings. As it is customary to think that homonymous meanings are stored in different lexical representations, the model of polysemy representation and storage has to be different from the sense enumeration lexicon some advocated in the past. The study of polysemy is, of course, based on the intrinsic nature of the languages and each language has its specific features in the field. Whereas, a more comprehensive study of peculiarities of the phenomenon like polysemy, the ability of words to have more than one meaning, can give a broader atmosphere and a good chance for an in-depth analysis of similar and various features of different systematic languages.

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